

CAGE: Cache-Aware Graphlet Enumeration

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Abstract. When information is (implicitly or explicitly) linked in its own nature, and is modeled as a network, retrieving patterns can benefit from this linked structure. In networks, “graphlets” (connected induced subgraphs of a given size k) are the counterparts of textual n -grams, as their frequency and shape can give powerful insights in the structure of a network and the role of its nodes. Differently from n -grams, the number of graphlets increases dramatically with their size k . We aim to push the exact enumeration of graphlets as far as possible, as enumeration (contrary to counting or approximation) gives the end-user the flexibility of arbitrary queries and restrictions on the graphlets found. For this, we exploit combinatorial and cache-efficient design strategies to cut the computational cost. The resulting algorithm CAGE (Cache-Aware Graphlet Enumeration) outperforms existing enumeration strategies by at least an order of magnitude, exhibiting a low number of L1-L2-L3 cache misses in the CPU. It is also competitive with the fastest known counting algorithms, without having their limitations on k .

1 Introduction

Information retrieval for textual documents can benefit from the discovery of patterns underlying the text, e.g. using n -grams (also q -grams, contiguous sequences of n items in a text) [25]. As most modern information is linked in nature, it can be modeled as a network. Patterns themselves can inherit this linked structure, and one of the fundamental tools are the so-called motifs, recurrent and statistically relevant patterns inside a network, i.e., frequent subgraphs: from the seminal papers of Milo et al. [17] and Pržulj [21] these are generally encoded in the form of k -*graphlets* (or, simply, graphlets), where k is usually kept small ($k \leq 5$). They are the natural candidates for having a role in network analysis, such as n -grams do in text analysis. The frequency and shape of graphlets can give powerful insights in the structure of a network and the role of its nodes.

Graphlets have found a remarkably wide range of applications; among many are finding the important nodes of a graph [3], comparing large graphs [26],

comparing temporal networks [2] or understanding the role of genes in pathways and cancer mechanisms [32]. There is also increasing interest over graphlets in the field of machine learning: one can extract information on the number of graphlets involving a node, or where a node occurs in it (i.e., its *orbit*), to produce graph kernels [26], or embeddings [6].

Formally, for a given undirected graph $G = (V, E)$, each set S of k nodes in G induces a subgraph $G[S] = (S, \{(x, y) \in E \mid x, y \in S\})$ by taking the corresponding edges from G . A k -graphlet of G is a set S of k nodes that induces a *connected* subgraph, namely, it satisfies the conditions $S \subseteq V$, $|S| = k$, and $G[S]$ is connected. A *graphlet enumeration algorithm* has G as input, and yields all sets S of G that are k -graphlets as output. An output example is in Fig. 1a.

Fig. 1. (a) an example graph with its 3-graphlets below; (b) k -graphlet count in the *Brady* network.

The key question addressed by this paper is “how far can we push graphlet enumeration algorithms?”. The question addresses the purest version of graphlet discovery, and its relevance is in building an efficient and general tool that can be exploited in any graphlet-related application. We will show a hard limit faced by current enumeration strategies, and how to overcome it.

The main challenge in this problem is the high computational cost involved. Differently from n -grams, the number of graphlets increases dramatically with the size k . Fig. 1b shows how graphlets increase exponentially with k , even in a small graph like the *Brady* network [14] (with 1,117 nodes and 1,330 edges). Existing approaches deal with this problem by keeping k small [1, 4, 11, 12, 16, 19, 20] (e.g., 3 or 4) if graphs are not very small, or by giving up exact results in favor of estimation [5, 7, 26, 29, 30]. Indeed, according to a recent survey on motifs [10], papers focused on estimation are becoming popular in recent years. For more related approaches, we refer the reader to the in-depth survey in [22].

1.1 Results

In this paper we develop a practical output-sensitive graphlet enumeration algorithm that is based on the classical binary partition scheme, a technique that induces a recursive tree, whose nodes are the recursive calls, and solutions are output in the leaves. We refine this strategy to take full advantage of cache memory, while also cutting down the size of the recursion tree beyond what is possible with current enumeration algorithms. Our contributions are as follows:

1. We empirically observed that current enumeration methods cannot further reduce their enumeration tree as the number of *failure* leaves, leaves which do not report a graphlet, is negligible (9% or less) even with simple strategies.
2. Based on this, we aim to go beyond the already good performance of simple enumerators: we achieve this by designing an algorithm that *better exploits cache memory* in the CPU, as we show using the Intel VTune Profiler. Intel CPUs have three cache levels (L1-L2-L3): L3 cache is faster but smaller than RAM (and typically shared among the CPU cores); L2 and L1 are even smaller and faster (typically one private L1-L2 per core). Our algorithm exhibits zero or few L3 cache misses (compared to RAM loads and stores) and L2-L3 cache-bound times have tiny values, in the range 0–5%.
3. Finally, we break through the hard limit on the number of recursive calls, *collapsing the three lowest levels of the recursion tree*. As the tree grows exponentially, this affects the largest levels. We also generate sets of solutions at once, in a compressed – yet easy to access – format.

We call the resulting algorithm CAGE (Cache-Aware Graphlet Enumeration), which constitutes an evolution of the reference enumeration algorithm [12], hereafter called KS-Simple (see Section 2), and outperforms it by *over an order of magnitude*. We evaluate CAGE against the state of the art, namely, KS-Simple, Kavosh [11], and FaSE [19], showing dramatically improved performance and scalability. We also include fast counting approaches [1, 20] that follow a more analytical method, showing they are more competitive; however, by design they cannot run for $k > 5$, whereas CAGE does not share this limitation.

In the rest of this paper, for an undirected graph $G = (V, E)$, the neighborhood of a node u is $N(u) = \{v \in V \mid (u, v) \in E\}$, the degree of u is $|N(u)|$, and Δ is the maximum degree among all nodes. For a set of nodes $S \subseteq V$, we define the neighborhood of S as $N(S) = \cup_{u \in S} N(u) \setminus S$, the distance-2 neighborhood as $N^2(S) = N(N(S)) \setminus (S \cup N(S))$ and the distance-3 neighborhood as $N^3(S) = N(N^2(S)) \setminus (S \cup N(S) \cup N^2(S))$.

2 Baseline Algorithm

The classical approach to list all k -graphlets in a graph $G = (V, E)$ is based on binary partition. Intuitively, for a graph $G = (V, E)$ and a node $v \in V$, we initialize $S = \{v\}$, and enumerate the k -graphlets containing v by considering a node $u \in N(S)$ and two cases: the k -graphlets containing u , and those that do

not. In the first case, enumeration continues with $S := S \cup \{u\}$, and k reduced to $k - 1$; in the second, with the same S and the k -graphlets in $G \setminus \{u\}$.¹ In particular, after setting an arbitrary scanning order for the nodes $v \in V$, each graphlet is built by recursively adding a member of $N(S)$ to S , after the initial call with $S = \{v\}$. We get to a recursive leaf when we reach one of the following:

- (*success leaf*) when $|S| = k$;
- (*failure leaf*) when $|S| < k$ and $|N(S)| = 0$.

One of the first algorithm able to enumerate all k -graphlets is ESU [31], while the current state-of-the-art algorithm is that of Komusiewicz and Sommer [12], hereafter called KS-Simple, that follows the above binary partition scheme, but with a clever optimization summarized below in Property 1.

Property 1 ([12]) *If a k -graphlet containing S does not exist in G after taking $u \in N(S)$ then no k -graphlet can exist in $G \setminus \{u\}$ with the same S .*

As an example, consider the graph in Fig. 1a while enumerating all 4-graphlets containing vertex b in $G \setminus \{a\}$. After the output of $\{b, c, d, e\}$, vertex e is removed and no more 4-graphlets (in particular containing b) exist. Thanks to Property 1 we can stop the computation as soon as the next recursive call, which will obviously fail. This property allows KS-Simple to have a running time of $O(k^2 \Delta)$ per graphlet.

3 The CAGE Algorithm

In this section we present our main contribution, the CAGE algorithm. We give the pseudocode and discuss its cache-awareness, carefully considering all the scenarios that the algorithm may encounter during its execution, and show how we can effectively compress the last three levels of its recursion tree.

3.1 Addressing a hard combinatorial limit

Before describing our algorithm, we introduce the principles behind its design.

First, we opted for a data-driven design and empirically observed that – on a dataset of over 150 graphs – the total number of failure leaves in the binary partition scheme is in fact orders of magnitude smaller than the total number of leaves, never surpassing 9%.

Second, we wanted to better exploit the cache in the CPU, the main motivation for this paper. For example, if we need to check whether an edge (x, y) exists and the adjacency list $N(x)$ is already in cache, whereas we have no such a guarantee for $N(y)$, it is clearly more efficient to test membership $y \in N(x)$ rather than $x \in N(y)$. Therefore, we carefully orchestrated the loading of graph data during execution (see comments in the pseudocode).²

¹ Here $G \setminus \{u\}$ is G without u and its incident edges.

² We are not directly controlling the cache, but rather allowing the algorithm to run cache-friendly by making standard assumptions on the associative cache [8].

Third, once some data is in the cache in the CPU, we would like to exploit it at its best before it is released to load further data. As $|S| < k$ and k is small, it is reasonable to assume that both S and $N(S)$ fit into the cache most of the times, as $|N(S)| < k\Delta$ (exceptions may occur for large Δ). Based on this, we stop the recursion when $|S| = k - 3$, and deduce all the possible extensions of S into graphlets by adding three further nodes. This greatly truncates the recursion tree, as each level of calls can be Δ times more populated than the previous one (potentially reducing the total number of calls by a $O(\Delta^3)$ factor).³ The last two principles are intimately connected to each other, and give a speedup of at least one order of magnitude in our experiments in Section 4.

3.2 Pseudocode

Algorithm 1 implements our principles stated above. It is called Cache-Aware Graphlet Enumeration (CAGE), and is a non-trivial and cache-aware extension of KS-Simple [12].

According to the first principle, we replaced the ENUM() function in KS-Simple with the one in Algorithm 1. We decided to keep the for loop of KS-Simple at lines 20–24, and fixed the scanning order of the vertices top-level loop for efficient memory usage: as we only look for the graphlets in which v is the smallest node of the order, we know all vertices smaller than v are in X , so we do not need to store them explicitly. The second and third principles are implemented at lines 2–19, as the base case. We observe that the base case is no more $|S| = k$ as in KS-Simple, but $|S| = k - 3$ as shown in Section 3.3. This is the outcome of several iterative improvements over KS-Simple.

3.3 Exploiting what is already cached

Consider S of size $|S| = k - 3$, and let v be the smallest node in S according to an arbitrary ordering (we use label ordering) of the vertices of G . As we have to extend S in all possible ways with 3 nodes, we pick them from $N(S)$, $N^2(S)$, and $N^3(S)$, ignoring the nodes belonging to X (or only reachable from S via X). Specifically, X is composed of the nodes $v' \in V$ such that $v' < v$, and of the nodes that have already been examined in the loop at lines 20–24 in the parent call. We only need to store explicitly the latter nodes.

When picking the 3 nodes, we have to deal with 4 different cases. They are discussed below with an accompanying drawing shown in Fig. 2.

Case 1: The 3 nodes come from $N(S) \setminus X$ (see line 4).

Case 2: A node u is from $N(S) \setminus X$, and the other 2 nodes are chosen from $N^2(S) \setminus X$ so that they are u 's neighbors (see lines 8 and 16).

Case 3: Distinct nodes u, v are from $N(S) \setminus X$, and the remaining node z is chosen from $N^2(S) \setminus X$, so that

- *Case 3a:* z is a common neighbor of both u and v (see lines 13 and 17), or

³ This idea can be generalized to $k - 4$, $k - 5$, and so on, but there is no payoff going further than $k - 3$ in practice as there are too many cases to handle.

Algorithm 1: CAGE: cache-efficient ENUM() algorithm, *solutions* is a global variable.

```

1 Function ENUM( $G, S, k, X$ ) // Hp.  $k > 3$  (case  $k = 3$  is simpler)
   // find all graphlets in  $G \setminus X$  containing all nodes in  $S$ 
2 if  $|N(S) \setminus X| = 0$  then return false // failure leaf
3 if  $|S| = k - 3$  then // exploit the cache to complete  $S$ 
4    $localcount \leftarrow \binom{|N(S) \setminus X|}{3}$  // (1) zero if  $|N(S) \setminus X| < 3$ 
5   forall  $u \in N(S) \setminus X$  do //  $N(S)$  loaded in cache
6      $udeg \leftarrow duplicated \leftarrow 0$ 
7     forall  $z \in (N(u) \setminus (N(S) \cup S)) \setminus X$  do //  $z \in N^2(S) \setminus X$ 
8       //  $N(u)$  and  $S$  loaded in cache
9        $udeg \leftarrow udeg + 1$  // needed for (2)
10      forall  $w \in (N(z) \setminus (N(S) \cup S)) \setminus X$  do // (4) see Fig. 2
11        //  $N(S), N(u), S$  cached, and  $N(z)$  loaded
12        if  $w \notin N(u)$  then  $localcount \leftarrow localcount + 1$ 
13      forall  $v \in (N(S) \setminus \{u, z\}) \setminus X$  do // (3)  $N(S), N(z)$  cached
14        if  $v \in N(z)$  then // (3a) counted twice, from  $v$  and  $z$ 
15           $duplicated \leftarrow duplicated + 1$ 
16        else // (3b)
17           $localcount \leftarrow localcount + 1$ 
18       $localcount \leftarrow localcount + \binom{udeg}{2}$  // (2) see Section 3.4
19       $localcount \leftarrow localcount + duplicated/2$  // (3a) duplicates
20      counted once
21  $solutions \leftarrow solutions + localcount$ 
22 return ( $localcount > 0$ )
23  $found \leftarrow false$ 
24 forall  $u \in N(S) \setminus X$  do // here  $|S| < k - 3$ . Vertices sorted by label
25   if ENUM( $G, S \cup \{u\}, k, X$ ) then  $found \leftarrow true$  else break
26    $X \leftarrow X \cup \{u\}$ 
27 return  $found$ 

```

- *Case 3b*: z is a neighbor of only u (symmetrically, only v) (see line 15).

Case 4: A node u is from $N(S) \setminus X$, a node z from $(N^2(S) \setminus X) \cap N(u)$, and the remaining node w from $N(z) \setminus (N(S) \cup S \cup N(u)) \setminus X$, which comes either from $N^3(S)$ or $N^2(S) \setminus N(u)$ (see line 10). As a result, CAGE is actually pruning the leaves, their parents, and their grandparents in the recursion tree, each time reducing the total number of calls roughly by a factor of Δ .

Fig. 2. Cases 1-4

As each case involves the same or fewer steps than KS-Simple [12], CAGE shares its worst-case running time guarantee:

Theorem 1. *CAGE reports all k -graphlets including the nodes in S , but not the nodes in X , in $O(k^2\Delta)$ time per graphlet using $O(\min\{k\Delta, |V|\})$ space.*

In order to make our implementation as cache-friendly as possible, we coupled the pruning of the recursion tree with some cache-friendly data structures so that S , $N(S) \setminus X$, and $N(u)$ are stored as vectors, $N(S)$ is stored as a cuckoo hash table [18], and X is not explicitly stored due to vertex ordering. We have:

Lemma 1. *Given an associative CPU cache [9], if its size is $\Omega(k\Delta)$ words of memory, then the base case $|S| = k - 3$ in CAGE loads S , $N(S)$, $N(u)$, and $N(z)$ once for distinct nodes u and z , and then keeps them in the cache when they are accessed.*

Comments in the pseudocode at lines 5–17 give indications when S , $N(S)$, $N(u)$, and $N(z)$ are loaded into cache, or already cached. This predicted behavior has been carefully planned during our experimental study. Moreover, the cache words used in practice are likely to be far less than the worst case $O(k\Delta)$, as real-world networks are sparse, with most vertices having very small degree.

3.4 Remarks

We did not discuss the case $k = 3$ as CAGE is mainly aimed at larger values of k , and it can be easily obtained as a simplification of the pseudocode. Moreover, for simplicity, we only report the number of solutions found, and the graphlets are not output. All algorithms in the experiments also do not make explicit output, as is usual when comparing enumeration algorithms [24]. Furthermore, CAGE can produce a compressed output, efficient to both read and write and a common practice in enumeration (see, e.g., [27, 28]): it suffices to output the $k - 3$ nodes in S , as well as the sets from which to choose the completions, e.g., for *case 1*, write the contents of S , followed by “plus any 3 elements from”, followed by the contents of $N(S) \setminus X$. When dealing with case 3a, we can decide to output only the choice $u < v$, to avoid the duplication when z is connected to both u and v .

4 Experimental Results

This section provides the details and results of our extensive experimental phase.

4.1 Environment and dataset

Our experiments were carried on a dual-processor Intel Xeon Gold 5318Y Icelake @ 2.10GHz machine, with 48 physical cores each and 1TB of shared RAM; private cache L1 per core: 48K, private cache L2 per core: 1.25MB, shared cache L3: 36MB, running Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS, Intel C++ compiler `icpx`, version 2022.1.0, and cache analysis was done with Intel VTune profiler, version 2022.2.0.

The dataset consists of 155 graphs taken from public repositories LASAGNE [14], Network Repository [23], and SNAP [13]. These files range in size from very small (hundreds of nodes and edges) to very large (millions of nodes and half a billion edges). Table 1 shows a relevant subset of the dataset, and the 10 graphs mentioned in this section can be downloaded from GitHub⁴, as well as the source code of our algorithm and the re-implemented KS-Simple.

Table 1. A sample from our dataset, sorted by $|E|$

Graph	Type	$ V $	$ E $	Δ
Brady	Biological	1,117	1,330	28
ca-GrQc	Collaboration	5,242	14,484	81
cti	Mesh	16,840	48,232	6
Wing	Mesh	62,032	121,544	4
Roadnet-TX	Road Network	1,379,917	1,921,660	12
Roadnet-CA	Road Network	1,965,206	2,766,607	12
Auto	Mesh	448,695	3,314,611	37
Hugetrace-00	DIMACS10	4,588,486	6,879,133	4
IMDB	Movies	913,201	37,588,613	11,941
Arabic-2005	Web Crawl	22,744,080	553,903,073	575,628

4.2 CAGE implementation and comparison methodology

We implemented CAGE in C++, compiled with the highest optimization flag `-O3`. The cache-friendly nature discussed in Algorithm 1 is enhanced by the `likely` and `unlikely` macros to help the compiler with branch prediction, and we do not physically delete and restore nodes between recursive calls by reusing the data structures mentioned in Section 3, e.g., traversing the vector for $N(S) \setminus X$ so that deletion of nodes is modeled by a flexible starting index.

Below we adopt the notation CAGE-1, CAGE-2, and CAGE-3, with the intent of distinguishing among the base cases $|S| = k - 1$, $|S| = k - 2$, and $|S| = k - 3$, respectively. Indeed, CAGE-3 is actually CAGE, and the others can be easily derived from by simplifying the pseudocode in Algorithm 1.

We compared our algorithms against several different algorithms from the literature, including recent and well known approaches from [22, Table 2], i.e., PGD [1], Kavosh [11], FaSE [19] and Escape [20] (although we exclude the matrix-based approach [16], unsuitable for large graphs), as well as the more recent KS-Simple [12]. The aforementioned methods adopt different strategies to exactly count the number of k -graphlets, but they all share an enumerative core, either via implicit counting (i.e., PGD and Escape) or explicit construction of the graphlets (the others). While we do not discuss their implementations for lack of space, we refer to their papers for the available sources. Since the available code of KS-Simple [12] is in Python, we reimplemented it in C++ to avoid

⁴ <https://github.com/DavideR95/CAGE>

penalizing it, following the same guidelines as for CAGE. We then conducted the following experiments:

- (i) Analysis of cache efficiency and hotspots in the code using VTune, setting a timeout of 15 minutes on a subset of the dataset built to represent differently sized graphs,
- (ii) Analysis of the recursion tree of KS-Simple for $k = 4, 5, 7, 9$ on the entire dataset with a time limit of 30 minutes, showing that the number of failure leaves is typically less than 1% of the total number of leaves, and never more than 9% (details omitted for space reasons),
- (iii) A stress test for all the algorithms and competitors, for $k \in [4, 10]$ with a timeout of 12 hours.

Table 2. VTune Profiler cache access statistics for our algorithms and competitors with $k = 7$. †: execution stopped after 15 minutes. *: execution stopped due to a memory allocation problem.

Graph	Algorithm	Time (s)	#Graphlets Found ($k = 7$)	L3 Misses	L1 Bound	L2 Bound	L3 Bound	Loads	Stores
ca-GrQc	KS-Simple †	†	8,577,821,416	0	7.9%	0.7%	0%	3,531 E+9	1,394 E+9
	Kavosh †	†	884,849,128	65,553,660	8.2%	0.3%	0.1%	3,075 E+9	1,782 E+9
	FaSE †	†	2,448,373,561	5,429,820	10.2%	0.7%	0%	1,912 E+9	276 E+9
	CAGE-1	76	15,186,322,814	0	8.8%	0.6%	0%	303 E+9	117 E+9
	CAGE-2	39	15,186,322,814	0	11.3%	1.5%	0%	116 E+9	7 E+9
	CAGE-3	34	15,186,322,814	0	15.4%	2.8%	0%	95 E+9	2 E+9
	roadnet-TX	KS-Simple	14	203,059,778	0	14.9%	0%	0%	43 E+9
Kavosh *		*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
FaSE		46	203,059,778	0	14.2%	0.5%	0%	128 E+9	37 E+9
CAGE-1		5	203,059,778	0	16.2%	0%	0.6%	14 E+9	8 E+9
CAGE-2		4	203,059,778	0	22.3%	0%	0%	6 E+9	2 E+9
CAGE-3		3	203,059,778	0	28.2%	0%	1.3%	5 E+9	1 E+9
auto	KS-Simple †	†	4,775,173,331	0	14.2%	0.3%	0%	2,360 E+9	1,051 E+9
	Kavosh *	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	FaSE †	†	3,032,335,810	27,202,000	12.5%	0.7%	0.1%	2,027 E+9	365 E+9
	CAGE-1 †	†	80,580,776,005	0	14.2%	0.3%	0%	2,176 E+9	1,014 E+9
	CAGE-2 †	†	135,096,265,408	0	21.9%	0.5%	0.1%	1,480 E+9	138 E+9
	CAGE-3 †	†	152,621,021,219	0	21.1%	1.4%	0.1%	2,080 E+9	53 E+9
arabic-2005	KS-Simple †	†	4,001,309,731	27,157,305	6%	0.7%	5.1%	3,626 E+9	593 E+9
	Kavosh *	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	FaSE *	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	CAGE-1 †	†	22,084,290,111,889	48,516,858	5.9%	0.8%	4.9%	2,976 E+9	552 E+9
	CAGE-2 †	†	27,208,214,120,342	21,697,928	7.8%	1%	4.2%	1,820 E+9	11 E+9
	CAGE-3 †	†	47,718,156,097,277	173,529,344	1%	0.3%	0.2%	3,329 E+9	23 E+9

4.3 Cache analysis

During our implementation of CAGE, we took our design decisions based upon the performance metrics given by Intel VTune Profiler, tweaking the code according to the statistics of cache accesses and misses. The results of the VTune analysis for the optimized versions of KS-Simple, CAGE-1, CAGE-2, and CAGE-3 are summarized in Table 2, along with the same data for our competitors

Kavosh [11] and FaSE [19]. We chose not to include PGD [1] and ESCAPE [20] in this analysis since they only work for $k \leq 5$, while our focus is on larger values of k , in order to show the performance scaling to larger working sets (i.e. larger S and $N(S)$). The macro rows correspond to four graphs, whose names are given in the first column. We report the cache performance by taking the best out of 5 non-consecutive executions of VTune, where the computation was stopped after 15 minutes for two large graphs⁵. The other columns report: the run time in seconds, number of graphlets found for $k = 7$, number of L3 cache misses (i.e. accesses to the RAM), how much L1, L2, L3 cache affected on the percentage of clock ticks where the CPU was stalled waiting on that level of cache (the lower, the better), and the total number of load and store operations.

From the results on our algorithms, it clearly emerges that L2 and L3 bounds are very small, whereas L1 is larger for small graphs. This is a sign of good cache usage, as the L2 and L3 cache misses are definitely more expensive than the L1 cache misses (both data and instructions). For the small graphs *ca-GrQc* and *roadnet-TX* and mid-size graph *auto*, we have zero L3 misses (as they probably fit in the L3); for large graph *arabic-2005*, the number of L3 cache misses increases going through the rows for KS-Simple, CAGE-1, CAGE-2, and CAGE-3. This may not be obvious as there is a timeout of 15 minutes for this large graph: consequently, KS-Simple produces very few solutions compared to the others, and CAGE-3 more solutions (the apparent anomaly for CAGE-3 on *arabic-2005* can be explained by dividing the numbers by 2 in its last row in the table, so that we roughly get the same number of solutions as CAGE-1 and CAGE-2, we have also similar numbers in the other columns, except for L3 misses, which we discuss in a while). The number of loads/stores follows a similar pattern to that for L3 misses. The number of L3 cache misses is negligible with respect to the total number of load and store instructions issued, allowing the percentage of L2- and L3-bound to stay always within 5%. On the other hand, our competitors are able to achieve similar results in terms of L1, L2, and L3 bound, but the number of L3 misses is higher even on *ca-GrQc*. FaSE is able to compute all the solutions with zero cache misses on *roadnet-TX*, but with a much higher time requirement compared to CAGE. Additionally, the Kavosh algorithm started having bad memory allocation⁶ issues already with *roadNet-TX*, while FaSE fails later on the largest graph.

We also evaluated the size of the data structures for $N(S)$, $N(u)$, and $N(z)$, examined during the for loop of Algorithm 1 along with the average degree of the networks, as shown in Table 3, for $k = 7$. They clearly fit into the cache most of the times, recalling that each node identifier is a 32-bit integer and that the L2 cache in each core is 1.25MB on our machine. For *arabic-2005*, even if its maximum degree Δ is large, its average degree is small, as well as the median

⁵ This timeout is due to the size of the data gathered by VTune, which grows quickly over time.

⁶ i.e. the runtime raised a `bad_alloc` exception or a segmentation fault while reading the input graph.

values for $N(\cdot)$. Lemma 1 indicates that CAGE-3 is cache-friendly under this condition on the average.

Table 3. Median size of $N(S)$, $N(u)$ and $N(z)$ for a subset of the dataset ($k = 7$).

Graph	Δ	avg. degree	$N(S)$	$N(u)$	$N(z)$
ca-GrQc	81	5.5	52	13	9
roadnet-TX	12	2.8	3	3	8
auto	37	14.7	35	15	15
arabic-2005	575,628	48.7	115	36	49

According to these results, we believe that CAGE-3 is preferable to CAGE-1 and CAGE-2 as it finds more solutions for the given time-out, even though in some cases CAGE-2 could perform as well as CAGE-3.

Finally, we remark that CAGE-4 (i.e., adopting $|S| = k - 4$ as base case) might not be faster than CAGE-3, as a recursive call needs to address 8 scenarios individually and explore $N^4(S)$ instead of $N^3(S)$: this increases code complexity, requires extensive fine-tuning and could reduce cache friendliness (adding nested for-loops and more load operations); as such we leave this study for future work.

Fig. 3. Running time of our competitors vs. CAGE on four significant input graphs. *: an execution issue occurred.

4.4 Running time analysis

Armed with our fine-tuned implementation of CAGE (i.e. CAGE-3), we compared it to the other methods mentioned in Section 4.2. We performed an extensive validation phase, measuring both the running time and the number of graphlets found, with a timeout of 12 hours. Some methods could not terminate the execution for some issues, e.g. they could not handle a graph so large, ran into memory issues, or were killed by the operating system.

Fig. 3 shows a summary of the results obtained in four graphs of increasing size, Brady, roadNet-TX, auto, and Hugetrace-0000 (see Table 1 for their characteristics). On the y-axis, we reported the running time in seconds, in logarithmic scale; on the x-axis, we report increasing values of $k \in [4, 10]$. For each value of k , each bar corresponds to an algorithm as specified in the legend, where lower bars mean better performances. The executions that had the issues mentioned above, have an asterisk ‘*’ in place of the corresponding bar. For graph auto, the executions for $k = 7, 8, 9, 10$ were in timeout (indicated with a bar).

We can observe that KS-Simple and CAGE perform quite well, with CAGE running faster than KS-Simple by roughly an order of magnitude (for $k = 7$ on auto, KS-Simple was in timeout whereas CAGE was the only one to terminate its execution). Both compare significantly better with the other methods, as the latter ones are either too slow or cannot execute that instance of the graph. An exception is the PGD algorithm [1], as it achieves faster running time than CAGE on Brady and auto, but it does not scale well for the other two graphs; moreover, PGD is explicitly designed to work only with $k = 3, 4$. These results, combined with the code profiling statistics of Section 4.3, confirm the benefits of our design principles for CAGE.

5 Conclusions

We presented CAGE, a cache-aware algorithm for k -graphlet enumeration that is an evolution of the classical binary partition technique. CAGE builds upon our empirical observation that binary partition produces only few failure leaves in the computational recursion tree. We developed and analyzed several variants of CAGE, iteratively cutting more recursion levels, that were fine-tuned during an extensive experimental phase based on cache analysis and number of graphlets reported. We believe CAGE can be used as the core for more sophisticated enumeration tasks, such as orbit enumeration or isomorphic graphlet classification [15, 21] as well as arbitrary user-defined queries, boosting analysis possibilities for large networks. Future work will consider applying the analysis capabilities of CAGE to graph analysis tasks, as well as attempting to increase the levels of recursion-tree pruning beyond 3.

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